

Internship proposal: Physics-informed deep learning for Womersley-fitted metrics in retinal Doppler holography: flow, viscosity, shear, wall motion, and impedance-like indices at cardiac harmonics

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Abstract

We reformulate the *point-spread-function* (PSF)-aware moving-wall Womersley (MW-W) inversion as a *physics-informed* learning problem to extract calibration-light, phase-referenced biomarkers from retinal Doppler holography (DH) *without* explicit wall segmentation or pulse-wave-velocity measurement. For each cardiac harmonic n , the complex velocity profile $V_n(r)$ is modeled as the PSF-convolved superposition of the rigid-wall Womersley basis B_n and its log-radius sensitivity Ψ_n . In the current classical pipeline, a weighted, complex least-squares (LS) step estimates the drive and moving-wall gains (C_n, D_n) at fixed (R_0, ν, h) , while a low-dimensional outer Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) loop refines (R_0, ν) (and optionally PSF meta-parameters) under explicit conditioning and adequacy criteria (SNR, residual RMS, condition number, PSF adequacy gain, ΔAICc). Within a fixed numerical aperture, DH measures RMS velocities from angle-averaged Doppler power, so that the reconstructed gains C_n , and therefore Q_n and τ_n , incorporate the vessel-by-vessel cosine factors averaged over the detection cone. No additional per-vessel cosine correction is required as long as the NA and interferometer geometry remain unchanged.

We embed this differentiable forward operator (with a differentiable PSF layer) into a gray-box Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN) that enforces weak-form harmonic Stokes/Womersley constraints, mass consistency via $K(\alpha_n)$, and physiological priors on viscosity and wall motion. The PINN estimates low-dimensional physical parameters $\theta = \{R_0, \nu, \{C_n, D_n\}\}$ and, with joint refinement of (R_0, ν) , yields per-harmonic volumetric flow $Q_n = \pi R_0^2 C_n K(\alpha_n)$, wall-shear stress τ_n , fractional wall kinematics $R_n/R_0 \simeq D_n/C_n$, and the local per-length impedance-like ratio $H_{G|Q}(\omega_n) = G_n/Q_n$ with $G_n = i\omega_n \rho C_n$. Here $H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)$ has units Pa s/m^4 and plays the role of a per-length pressure-gradient-to-flow transfer function; we often report its geometry-normalised magnitude $|H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)| R_0^2$ (units Pa s/m^2), which behaves like an effective surface impedance per unit pulsatile flow.

To stabilise training and preserve compatibility with the existing pipeline, the PINN is weakly supervised by QC-filtered medians of angle-robust Tier 1 metrics (ratios and phases) obtained from the classical LS+LM MW-W inversion, which act as soft teacher signals at segment and eye levels rather than as hard labels. We report flow-referenced transfers $H_{R|Q,n} = (R_n/R_0)/Q_n$, $H_{\tau|Q,n} = \tau_n/Q_n$ and their phases $\phi_{R|Q,n}, \phi_{\tau|Q,n}, \phi_{G|Q,n}$, plus AC energetics $\mathcal{P}'_{\text{diss},n} = \frac{1}{2}\Re\{G_n Q_n^*\}$ and $\mathcal{P}'_{\text{store},n} = \frac{1}{2}\Im\{G_n Q_n^*\}$. Multi-harmonic fitting shares (R_0, ν) across n and enables time-domain shear indices (TAWSS/OSI/RRT) from $n \leq 2$. Compared with nested LS+LM inversion, the PINN improves identifiability at low SNR and small α_n , mitigates rim bias via the PSF layer, and provides principled uncertainty (bootstrap/ensembles/Laplace) with trial-ready QC gates that remain anchored to the historical LS MW-W metrics. Because inference is amortised through a trained network, applying the model to thousands of segments reduces to fast forward passes, enabling robust, uncertainty-aware Womersley-fitted metrics to be deployed at scale across centres and devices.

1 Introduction

The retinal circulation offers a uniquely accessible window onto human microvascular health. Doppler holography (DH) extends conventional fundus imaging by encoding the complex optical field and its temporal dynamics, enabling angle-resolved measurements of pulsatile blood-flow velocity in individual retinal vessels. Beyond mean flow, the full cardiac waveform at each spatial location carries information about viscosity, vessel wall mechanics, and pressure-flow coupling, all of which are relevant to systemic cardiovascular, metabolic, and neurodegenerative disease.

To turn these rich recordings into biomarkers that can support large clinical studies, we require a compact set of quantitative, physically interpretable metrics: volumetric flow and its harmonics, wall-shear stress, fractional radius pulsation, and impedance-like indices that link driving pressure gradients to flow and shear. A natural framework for this is the Womersley model of pulsatile flow in compliant tubes. In previous work, we have used a PSF-aware moving-wall Womersley (MW-W) inversion to recover, harmonic by harmonic, the radius R_0 , an effective viscosity ν , and complex gains (C_n, D_n) from DH-derived velocity profiles.

The current classical MW-W pipeline proceeds in two layers. For each harmonic and segment, a weighted, complex LS fit estimates (C_n, D_n) at fixed (R_0, ν, h) , while an outer LM loop refines (R_0, ν) (and optionally PSF meta-parameters) under explicit QC and identifiability criteria: harmonic SNR, residual magnitude and phase RMS, condition number $\kappa(X_n)$ of the PSF-blurred design matrix, and PSF adequacy gain and ΔAICc versus a no-PSF model. Within a fixed numerical aperture, DH measures angle-averaged RMS velocities, so the fitted coefficients C_n , and hence Q_n and τ_n , already incorporate the cosine factors averaged over the detection cone; there is no need for per-vessel cosine correction, provided NA and interferometer geometry are stable.

However, classical MW-W inversion via nested LS+LM still faces several challenges when deployed at scale in noisy, heterogeneous clinical data. PSF blur makes the rigid basis B_n and its log-radius sensitivity Ψ_n nearly collinear at small Womersley number α_n , degrading identifiability of wall motion and viscosity. Angle errors and residual segmentation artefacts can bias rim velocities, and the two-stage inversion (inner linear regression, outer non-linear refinement) does not exploit cross-harmonic coherence or informative physiological priors in a principled way. When ν is left free, extreme apparent viscosities ν_{app} and unstable (D_n/C_n) in these regimes are best interpreted as signatures of an under-determined inverse problem rather than as true physiology. In practice, the current pipeline often fixes ν at a subject-level value (e.g. $\nu_0 = 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) and treats any segment-wise ν_{app} preferred by the fit as a QC diagnostic rather than as a biomarker.

In this note, we recast the PSF-aware MW-W inversion as a gray-box Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN). Instead of learning arbitrary velocity fields, the PINN learns low-dimensional physical parameters $\theta = \{R_0, \nu, \{C_n, D_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}\}$ through a differentiable forward model that explicitly encodes the Womersley basis, its log-radius sensitivity, and a convolutional PSF layer. Weak-form Stokes/Womersley residuals, mass consistency, and physiological priors on $(R_0, \nu, D_n/C_n)$ act as regularisers that stabilise the inversion at low SNR and small α_n . A multi-harmonic design shares (R_0, ν) across cardiac harmonics and directly outputs flow-referenced transfers and their phases.

Crucially, we do not discard the existing LS+LM MW-W pipeline. For segments that pass stringent QC, we compute Tier 1 metrics (angles and ratios) and aggregate them into QC-filtered medians at the level of each eye, vessel class, or scan. These medians, together with segment-level LS metrics, serve as soft teacher signals for the PINN via additional loss terms. This teacher-student scheme lets the PINN inherit the behaviour of the classical inversion in well-posed regimes while relying on physics and data to extrapolate into ill-conditioned regions. In other words, the LS+LM solver becomes a *teacher* for the network where it is trustworthy, and the PINN becomes a *regularised, amortised* version of the inversion where LS+LM is fragile.

Beyond stabilising the inversion, the PINN formulation enables explicit uncertainty quantification (through bootstrap, ensembles, and Laplace approximations) and amortised inference: once trained, evaluating the model on a new segment is a single forward pass, rather than a nested LS+LM solve. This is key for multi-site deployment and cohort-scale analyses.

The rest of this document is organised as follows. [Section 2](#) specifies the inputs, outputs, and motivation for the PINN formulation. [Section 4](#) details the gray-box architecture, loss terms, and training protocol, including uncertainty quantification and LS-guided regularisation. Subsequent sections formalise the notation and MW-W forward model, define flow-referenced transfers and time-domain shear indices, discuss an angle policy and AC energetics, and summarise estimation, QC, and reporting practices suitable for multi-site clinical cohorts.

Contributions

- PSF-aware, multi-harmonic PINN estimating $\{R_0, \nu, C_n, D_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}$ and deriving $Q_n, \tau_n, R_n/R_0, H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)$ with uncertainty, using a gray-box architecture where the neural network only parametrises low-dimensional physical quantities and their dependence on the input profiles.
- Improved identifiability at low SNR/small α_n via weak-form constraints, mass consistency, and ratio priors on D_n/C_n , especially in regimes where the classical LS+LM inversion produces extreme ν_{app} or unstable wall-motion estimates.
- Distillation of QC-filtered medians from the classical LS+LM MW-W inversion into the PINN through soft teacher losses, aligning PINN outputs with established Tier 1 metrics at segment and eye levels in well-posed regimes while allowing physics and data to dominate in ill-conditioned regimes.
- Trial-ready, angle-robust transfers $H_{R|Q,n}, H_{\tau|Q,n}$ and phases $\phi_{R|Q,n}, \phi_{\tau|Q,n}, \phi_{G|Q,n}$ with explicit QC and reporting, including time-domain shear indices (TAWSS/OSI/RRT) and AC energetics per length.
- Amortised, portable inference across sites and devices: once trained, the PINN replaces repeated LS+LM solves by fast forward passes, enabling cohort-scale processing and making the inversion robust to missing or noisy auxiliary inputs by learning from realistic PSF/SNR variability.
- End-to-end uncertainty quantification (cycle bootstrap, ensembles, Laplace approximation) and multi-scale QC that are integrated into the estimator itself rather than applied as purely post-hoc filters, yielding metrics that are both interpretable and equipped with confidence intervals.

2 What goes in, what comes out, and why a PINN?

Inputs (per segment). Cardiac-locked complex profiles $\{V_n(r_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_r}, n \in \mathcal{N}$; the fundamental angular frequency ω_0 ; a PSF descriptor h (empirical or meta-parametric); optional artery/vein label and axial coordinate z ; priors or bounds on ν ; and radial weights $W_n(r)$ encoding SNR/coherence and rim tapering. For segments already processed by the classical LS+LM MW-W pipeline, associated Tier 1 metrics (ratios, phases) and their QC flags can be provided as optional teacher targets.

Outputs. The PINN outputs $\{\widehat{R}_0, \widehat{\nu}, \widehat{C}_n, \widehat{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}$, from which it derives $\widehat{Q}_n, \widehat{\tau}_n, \widehat{R}_n/\widehat{R}_0, \widehat{H}_{G|Q}(\omega_n), \widehat{H}_{R|Q,n}, \widehat{H}_{\tau|Q,n}$, phases $\widehat{\phi}_{R|Q,n}, \widehat{\phi}_{\tau|Q,n}, \widehat{\phi}_{G|Q,n}$, and AC energetics $\widehat{\mathcal{P}}^l$, together with QC metrics and uncertainty summaries (bootstrap/ensemble intervals, viscosity-propagation estimates). At the cohort level, we report QC-filtered medians and interquartile ranges of these quantities

across segments, along with explicit flags on which metrics come primarily from LS+LM, from the PINN, or from their combination.

Why a PINN instead of “just” better LS+LM? The aim is not to replace a well-posed inversion by a black box, but to extend and regularise it:

- **Better identifiability in hard regimes.** When α_n is small, PSF blur is strong, or SNR is modest, LS+LM becomes ill-conditioned and uses ν or D_n as “garbage parameters” to absorb residual mismatch. The PINN uses weak-form physics, priors, and cross-harmonic sharing to stabilise $\{R_0, \nu, C_n, D_n\}$ and recover usable flow/shear/impedance metrics where LS+LM alone fails.
- **Joint treatment of physics, priors, and QC.** Classical inversion uses physics inside the forward model but handles priors and QC via outer heuristics. The PINN packs data misfit, physics residuals, priors, PSF adequacy, and LS-based teacher terms into a single differentiable loss, allowing the optimisation to automatically balance them.
- **Teacher-student continuity.** The existing LS+LM MW-W pipeline is used as a teacher where it is reliable (high-quality segments), so that the PINN behaves like the historical pipeline in well-posed regimes and only deviates when the physics+data evidence calls for it.
- **Uncertainty and amortised inference.** LS+LM typically returns point estimates per segment. The PINN supports bootstrap and ensemble-based uncertainty and, once trained, turns inversion into a cheap forward pass — crucial when processing large multi-site cohorts.
- **Robustness to missing/messy inputs.** By training on realistic perturbations of PSF descriptors, SNR, and harmonic content, the network learns to cope with incomplete or degraded inputs in a way that static LS+LM cannot.

3 Assumptions and Validity Regime

1. Axisymmetric, straight, quasi-cylindrical segments; orthogonal slicing; exclude bifurcations/curvature.
2. Small wall motion: $|R_n|/R_0 \ll 1$ (first-order moving-wall term).
3. Linear time-invariant behavior over the gated window; ν constant over $n \in \mathcal{N}$.
4. Shift-invariant radial PSF; convolutional PSF layer sufficient (no anisotropic blur).
5. Fixed numerical aperture and interferometer geometry so that DH measures angle-averaged RMS velocities; no per-vessel cosine correction is applied or required for C_n, Q_n, τ_n .

4 Method Overview: Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN)

4.1 Model choice and architecture

Gray-box latent physics. We adopt a gray-box formulation in which the trainable parameters are low-dimensional physical quantities rather than free-field values. For each segment and harmonic set \mathcal{N} , the latent parameter vector is

$$\theta = \{R_0, \nu, \{C_n, D_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}\}.$$

Here R_0 is the baseline vessel radius, ν the (apparent) kinematic viscosity shared across harmonics, and $C_n, D_n \in \mathbb{C}$ are, respectively, the drive and moving-wall gains of the PSF-aware moving-wall Womersley model at harmonic n .

The differentiable physics layer implements the forward operator that maps θ to predicted data-space harmonic profiles $\widehat{V}_n(r)$. For each harmonic,

$$\widehat{V}_n(r) = (\widehat{C}_n B_n(r; \widehat{R}_0, \widehat{\alpha}_n)) \star h + (\widehat{D}_n \Psi_n(r; \widehat{R}_0, \widehat{\alpha}_n)) \star h, \quad \widehat{\alpha}_n = \widehat{R}_0 \sqrt{\omega_n / \widehat{\nu}},$$

where B_n and $\Psi_n = \partial B_n / \partial \ln R$ are the rigid-wall Womersley basis and its log-radius sensitivity, \star denotes convolution with the radial PSF proxy h , and $\omega_n = n\omega_0$ is the cardiac angular frequency. This layer is fully differentiable with respect to all components of θ (and PSF meta-parameters), so gradients can backpropagate through the physics to update both geometric/rheological parameters and the harmonic gains.

Backbone. Above this physics layer, we use a small shared backbone to encode the input harmonic profiles and auxiliary meta-data into a compact latent representation. Practically, we employ a lightweight MLP encoder per harmonic n , fed with the radial samples of $V_n(r)$ after basic normalization (e.g. by $\|V_1\|_2$) and coordinate encoding. To preserve high-frequency structure in r , this encoder can use either Fourier feature mappings or sinusoidal activation networks (SIREN-type) as front-end layers.

The per-harmonic embeddings are then fused with global context: PSF descriptors (e.g. FWHM and shape parameters), the fundamental frequency f_0 , optional artery/vein labels, and axial position. This fused latent vector is fed to two heads:

- a global head predicting the shared geometry and rheology (R_0, ν) ;
- per-harmonic heads predicting the complex gains (C_n, D_n) for $n \in \mathcal{N}$.

To enforce physiological plausibility and stabilise optimisation, (R_0, ν) are produced via a softplus+affine transformation:

$$R_0 = a_R + b_R \text{softplus}(z_R), \quad \nu = a_\nu + b_\nu \text{softplus}(z_\nu),$$

with learned or fixed offsets (a_R, a_ν) and scales (b_R, b_ν) chosen so that the resulting values remain within realistic ranges for retinal arteries and veins. This keeps the network in a well-posed regime, avoids negative radii or viscosities, and lets the rest of the loss function act as a refinement rather than as a hard constraint-enforcement mechanism. The same ranges are chosen to be consistent with the priors used in the current LS+LM pipeline (see below).

Amortised inference and deployment. Once trained, the PINN replaces per-segment LS+LM solves by a single forward pass through the backbone and physics layer. This amortisation has two practical consequences:

- computational cost per segment becomes predictable and small, which is essential when processing tens of thousands of segments in large cohorts or multi-site trials;
- the learned mapping implicitly captures typical PSF/SNR variability across acquisitions, making the inversion more robust to realistic deviations from the ideal forward model than a purely analytic LS+LM solve.

From an internship perspective, the student will first implement and validate the PINN on a subset of data, then benchmark its runtime and robustness against the classical inversion on larger cohorts.

4.2 Training objective and regularization

The total loss combines a data–misfit term in profile space with several physics–informed, prior, and teacher terms that improve identifiability and robustness:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\Theta) = & \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \|W_n(r) [\widehat{V}_n(r; \widehat{\theta}, h) - V_n(r)]\|_2^2 + \lambda_{\text{weak}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{weak}} + \lambda_{\text{mass}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{mass}} + \lambda_{\text{pri}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{pri}} + \lambda_{\text{psf}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{psf}} \\ & + \lambda_{\text{teach,seg}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,seg}} + \lambda_{\text{teach,med}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,med}}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where Θ collects all network weights and $\widehat{\theta}$ denotes the predicted physical parameters. The first term is a weighted complex least–squares misfit between measured and predicted harmonic profiles in data space, with radial weights $W_n(r)$ that encode SNR/coherence and rim tapering.

Weak-form Womersley/Stokes constraints. The term $\mathcal{L}_{\text{weak}}$ enforces the governing equations in weak form:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{weak}} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_k \left| \int_0^1 \phi_k(x) \mathcal{R}_n(\widehat{v}_n(x)) x dx \right|^2. \quad (2)$$

Here $\widehat{v}_n(x)$ is the predicted complex velocity profile in the normalised radius $x = r/R_0$, ϕ_k are test functions (e.g. low–order polynomials or compactly supported basis functions), and \mathcal{R}_n is the radial Stokes/Womersley residual operator at harmonic n . This term pushes the network to produce profiles that are not only close to the data, but also compatible with the underlying linear harmonic flow equations in aggregate, which greatly improves stability and identifiability at low SNR and small Womersley number α_n .

Mass/flow consistency. The term $\mathcal{L}_{\text{mass}}$ ties the pointwise predicted profiles back to the Womersley–predicted flow:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{mass}} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \left| 2\pi \int_0^{\widehat{R}_0} \widehat{v}_n^{\text{model}}(r) r dr - \widehat{Q}_n \right|^2, \quad \widehat{Q}_n = \pi \widehat{R}_0^2 \widehat{C}_n K(\widehat{\alpha}_n). \quad (3)$$

The first integral computes the volumetric flow directly from the modelled velocity profile, while \widehat{Q}_n is the analytic Womersley flow for the same $(\widehat{R}_0, \widehat{v}, \widehat{C}_n)$. Penalising their mismatch enforces internal consistency between the physics layer and the learned profiles, and prevents pathological solutions where the profile fit is good but the implied flow is unphysical.

Physiological priors. We encode soft priors on viscosity, radius, and wall–motion ratios via

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pri}} = \beta_\nu \Phi_{\text{range}}(\widehat{\nu}) + \beta_R \Phi_{\text{range}}(\widehat{R}_0) + \beta_D \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \Phi_{\text{ratio}}\left(\frac{\widehat{D}_n}{\widehat{C}_n}\right). \quad (4)$$

The functions Φ_{range} penalise departures from prescribed intervals using smooth barriers (e.g. squared distance to the nearest bound), while Φ_{ratio} penalises excessive wall–motion ratios $|\widehat{D}_n/\widehat{C}_n|$ beyond physiologically reasonable levels. This stabilises the inversion in regimes where the moving–wall component is weakly identifiable and discourages the network from using unrealistic wall motion to compensate for PSF or noise artefacts.

PSF adequacy and identifiability. Finally, \mathcal{L}_{psf} regulates the PSF meta–parameters and rewards models that genuinely benefit from PSF–awareness:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{psf}} = \beta_{\text{psf}} \Phi_{\text{range}}(\text{FWHM}_{\text{PSF}}) - \gamma_{\text{gain}} \Delta \mathcal{E}, \quad \Delta \mathcal{E} = \frac{\mathcal{E}_{\text{no-PSF}} - \mathcal{E}_{\text{PSF}}}{\mathcal{E}_{\text{no-PSF}}}. \quad (5)$$

The first term constrains the PSF FWHM to realistic optical values, while the second term favours PSF settings that significantly improve the data–fit energy \mathcal{E} compared with a no–PSF model. In practice, we mirror the current LS+LM pipeline by requiring a median PSF adequacy gain of at least 0.2 and an information–criterion improvement $\Delta\text{AICc} \geq 2$ for accepting PSF–aware settings; otherwise, a simpler or shared PSF is preferred. This prevents overfitting via unbounded PSF blur or shrinkage and embeds, at the loss level, the adequacy criteria that would otherwise be checked post hoc.

Numeric priors (typical). To remain consistent with the current classical inversion, we use broad but physiologically motivated numeric ranges:

$$\nu \in [1.5, 4.0] \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}, \quad R_0 \sim 100 \mu\text{m} \text{ with priors (artery/vein)}, \quad \text{FWHM}_{\text{PSF}} \in [0.1, 0.5] R_0,$$

with a soft prior $|D_n/C_n| \lesssim 0.06$ for the first few harmonics and α_1 typically in the range 0.5–3 induced by (R_0, ν) . These priors are sufficiently loose not to dominate the data, but tight enough to regularise ill–conditioned regimes (small α_n , strong blur, low SNR). In a first deployment stage, ν can be fixed to a subject–level value (e.g. $3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$), with the prior range interpreted as a band for uncertainty propagation rather than as a parameter to be freely optimised per segment.

Guidance from QC-filtered LS MW–W inversion. The existing PSF–aware LS+LM MW–W pipeline remains the primary reference for *legacy* metrics. For segments that pass strict QC (SNR, residual RMS, PSF adequacy gain, ΔAICc , $\kappa(X_n)$), we compute LS–derived Tier 1 metrics such as

$$\{H_{G|Q}(\omega_1), H_{\tau|Q,1}, H_{R|Q,1}, \phi_{G|Q,1}, \phi_{\tau|Q,1}, \phi_{R|Q,1}, R_1/R_0\},$$

and we aggregate them into QC–filtered medians per eye or vessel class.

We use these quantities as *soft* teacher signals for the PINN in two complementary ways:

- **Segment-level teacher loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,seg}}$:** on a subset \mathcal{S}_{HQ} of high–quality segments, the PINN–derived metrics $\tilde{m}_{j,k}$ are gently nudged towards their LS+LM counterparts $\hat{m}_{j,k}$ for a small set \mathcal{K}_{seg} of robust Tier 1 metrics:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,seg}} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{HQ}}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{seg}}} w_{j,k} d_k(\tilde{m}_{j,k}, \hat{m}_{j,k}), \quad (6)$$

where d_k is a Euclidean distance in log–magnitude space for positive scalars and a circular distance for phases.

- **Median-level teacher loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,med}}$:** for each eye/subject s , we compute QC–filtered medians $\hat{m}_{s,k}^{\text{med}}$ over segments that pass LS+LM QC, and compare them to the medians $\tilde{m}_{s,k}^{\text{med}}$ of the corresponding PINN metrics across *all* segments:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,med}} = \sum_s \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{med}}} w_{s,k} |\tilde{m}_{s,k}^{\text{med}} - \hat{m}_{s,k}^{\text{med}}|^2. \quad (7)$$

Here \mathcal{K}_{med} is a small set of distribution–level metrics (e.g. median $|H_{G|Q}(\omega_1)|$, $\phi_{G|Q,1}$, $\phi_{\tau|Q,1}$, TAWSS, OSI).

Both teacher losses are applied with modest weights $\lambda_{\text{teach,seg}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{teach,med}}$, so that physics and data remain the primary drivers of the solution, while the LS+LM MW–W metrics gently anchor the PINN to the behaviour of the historical pipeline in well–posed regimes. This distillation strategy also ensures a smooth transition for downstream users, who can continue to interpret the metrics in terms of the familiar LS+LM MW–W outputs.

4.3 Training protocol

Data pre-processing and splits. Training is performed with subject-wise splits to avoid information leakage between training and validation sets. For each segment, we normalise the complex harmonic profiles $\{V_n(r)\}$ by $\|V_1\|_2$, and map the radial coordinate to the unit interval, $r \rightarrow x \in [0, 1]$, using an initial radius estimate. PSF descriptors and meta-data (artery/vein label, axial span, etc.) are standardised per acquisition. Where available, LS+LM MW-W results and QC flags are carried alongside the DH data to build \mathcal{S}_{HQ} and the per-eye medians.

Initialisation and optimisation schedule. To accelerate convergence and reduce the risk of unphysical local minima, we warm-start the PINN from the classical two-layer inversion (weighted LS for (C_n, D_n) at fixed (R_0, ν) followed by a low-dimensional LM refinement over (R_0, ν, PSF) where appropriate). These initial values are injected into the output heads or used to initialise the last-layer weights.

The main training phase uses Adam with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} decayed to 10^{-5} with cosine annealing over 5×10^3 to 2×10^4 steps, depending on the dataset size and number of harmonics. Once the network has converged in a stochastic sense, we optionally apply a short Gauss-Newton or Levenberg-Marquardt polish (10–50 iterations) on the physical parameters $\hat{\theta}$ using the full-batch loss, treating the backbone as fixed. This last step improves the curvature-aware fit of $(R_0, \nu, \{C_n, D_n\})$ without re-training the feature extractor.

Continuation and weighting of physics and teacher terms. We adopt a continuation strategy for the physics-informed and teacher penalties. Early in training, the focus is on matching the data:

- λ_{weak} is ramped gradually from 0 to a target value (typically ≈ 0.5), so that weak-form constraints are introduced once the data-fit is reasonable.
- λ_{mass} and λ_{psf} are started relatively high to enforce global mass consistency and PSF plausibility, then relaxed once the model has settled into a physically coherent regime.
- $\lambda_{\text{teach,seg}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{teach,med}}$ are initially set to zero, then slowly increased to small positive values once the PINN has reached a baseline solution. This prevents the teacher losses from forcing the network to mimic LS+LM artefacts too early, while still aligning the PINN with QC-filtered LS+LM medians at convergence.

This schedule prevents the network from being locked into a poor basin early on by overly rigid constraints. We monitor convergence with a validation set and apply early stopping with a patience of about 300 steps, based on the total loss or on a composite metric that emphasises Tier 1 outputs (e.g. reproducibility of angle-invariant ratios and phases).

Uncertainty quantification. Uncertainty on the estimated physical parameters and derived metrics is assessed by combining three complementary approaches:

- **Cycle bootstrap.** For each segment, we resample cardiac cycles with replacement, recompute the input harmonics, and re-evaluate the trained PINN. This yields bootstrap distributions and confidence intervals for $\hat{\theta}$ and downstream quantities (e.g. $|Q_n|, |\tau_n|, R_n/R_0, H_{\tau|Q}$, phases).
- **Ensemble restarts.** We train 5–10 independent model instances with different random initialisations and data shuffles. The dispersion across ensemble predictions captures epistemic (model) uncertainty and guards against single-run idiosyncrasies.

- **Laplace approximation.** After the Gauss–Newton/LM polish on $\hat{\theta}$, we approximate the local posterior around the optimum by a diagonal–Hessian Gaussian (Laplace approximation). This provides cheap approximate marginal variances for the physical parameters, which can be propagated analytically or numerically to derived metrics.

Combined, these tools provide trial–ready uncertainty bands and QC metrics at the segment and subject levels, enabling robust reporting of Womersley–fitted flow, shear, wall–motion, and impedance–like indices in multi–site clinical cohorts.

5 Notation and Forward Model (All Harmonics)

Coordinates/signals. $r \geq 0$, $x = r/R_0$; $t \in \mathbb{R}$; $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0$; $\omega_n = n\omega_0$. Velocity $v(r, t)$, complex harmonic profile $V_n(r) \in \mathbb{C}$.

Womersley bases (per n).

$$\alpha_n = R_0 \sqrt{\omega_n/\nu}, \quad \lambda_n = e^{i3\pi/4} \alpha_n, \quad B_n(x) = 1 - \frac{J_0(\lambda_n x)}{J_0(\lambda_n)},$$

$$\Psi_n(x) = \frac{\partial B_n}{\partial \ln R} = -\frac{\lambda_n J_1(\lambda_n)}{J_0(\lambda_n)^2} J_0(\lambda_n x), \quad K(\alpha_n) = 1 - \frac{2J_1(\lambda_n)}{\lambda_n J_0(\lambda_n)} \in \mathbb{C}.$$

PSF-aware forward model (per n).

$$V_n(r) \approx (C_n B_n(r; R_0, \alpha_n)) \star h + (D_n \Psi_n(r; R_0, \alpha_n)) \star h.$$

Physical mapping (per n).

$$G_n = i \omega_n \rho C_n, \quad Q_n = \pi R_0^2 C_n K(\alpha_n), \quad \tau_n = \frac{\mu C_n \lambda_n J_1(\lambda_n)}{R_0 J_0(\lambda_n)}, \quad \frac{R_n}{R_0} \approx \frac{D_n}{C_n}.$$

Here R_n denotes the complex n -th harmonic of the radius, so that, under the small wall–motion assumption, $R(t) \approx R_0 + \Re\{\sum_{n \geq 1} R_n e^{i\omega_n t}\}$.

Angle-averaged velocities and NA. Within each segment, DH measures Doppler power integrated over a fixed detection cone set by the numerical aperture. After calibration, this power is converted into RMS blood–flow velocities already averaged over the local distribution of beam–flow angles inside that cone. Consequently, any real multiplicative scaling of the measured velocities (e.g. from calibration uncertainty, NA changes, or uniform rescaling of Doppler sensitivity) multiplies C_n and D_n by the same real factor and therefore cancels in all ratios G_n/Q_n , $(R_n/R_0)/Q_n$, τ_n/Q_n . There is no need for per–vessel cosine correction by a single beam–axis angle, and the residual absolute scaling uncertainty stems from the global velocity calibration (NA, magnification, interferometer geometry), not from vessel–to–vessel angle differences.

6 Flow-Referenced Transfers and Phases (per Harmonic)

Dilatation per unit pulsatile flow.

$$H_{R|Q}(\omega_n) = \frac{(R_n/R_0)}{Q_n} = \frac{D_n/C_n}{\pi R_0^2 K(\alpha_n)}, \quad \phi_{R|Q,n} = \arg H_{R|Q}(\omega_n) = \arg(D_n/C_n) - \arg K(\alpha_n).$$

Shear per unit pulsatile flow.

$$H_{\tau|Q}(\omega_n) = \frac{\tau_n}{Q_n} = \frac{\mu}{\pi R_0^3 K(\alpha_n)} \frac{\lambda_n J_1(\lambda_n)}{J_0(\lambda_n)}, \quad \phi_{\tau|Q,n} = \arg H_{\tau|Q}(\omega_n).$$

Impedance-like (per length).

$$H_{G|Q}(\omega_n) = \frac{G_n}{Q_n} \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \phi_{G|Q,n} = \arg (H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)).$$

Here $H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)$ has units Pa s/m⁴ and can be interpreted as a per-length pressure–gradient–to–flow transfer function. For reporting we often use the geometry–normalised magnitude $|H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)| R_0^2$, which has units Pa s/m² and behaves like an effective surface impedance per unit pulsatile flow. In analogy with classical vascular impedance $Z(\omega) = \Delta p(\omega)/Q(\omega)$, one may write $Z(\omega) \approx H_{G|Q}(\omega) L$ for a segment of length L .

Phase relations (diagnostic). Since $Q_n \propto C_n K(\alpha_n)$,

$$\arg H_{G|Q}(\omega_n) = \frac{\pi}{2} - \arg K(\alpha_n), \quad \Rightarrow \quad \phi_{R|Q,n} - \phi_{G|Q,n} = \arg\left(\frac{D_n}{C_n}\right) - \frac{\pi}{2},$$

$$\phi_{\tau|Q,n} - \phi_{G|Q,n} = \arg\left(\frac{\lambda_n J_1(\lambda_n)}{J_0(\lambda_n)}\right) - \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

Equal phases arise only for specific parameter values (e.g. $\arg(D_n/C_n) = \pi/2$ or special α_n).

7 Time-Domain Shear Indices

With $\tau(t) = \Re\{\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \tau_n e^{i\omega_n t}\}$ and period $T = 2\pi/\omega_0$,

$$\text{TAWSS} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T |\tau(t)| dt, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{OSI} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\left| \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \tau(t) dt \right|}{\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T |\tau(t)| dt} \right), \quad (9)$$

$$\text{RRT} = \frac{1}{(1 - 2 \text{OSI}) \text{TAWSS}}. \quad (10)$$

Discrete evaluation uses the $n \leq 2$ reconstruction sampled at N_t uniform times.

8 Angle Policy

Phases and ratios ($\phi_{R|Q,n}$, $\phi_{\tau|Q,n}$, $\phi_{G|Q,n}$, $|H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)|$ ratios, and $|H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)| R_0^2$) are angle–invariant and calibration–light: any real velocity gain factor multiplies C_n and D_n equally and cancels in these quantities. Absolute magnitudes ($|Q_n|$, $|\tau_n|$, \mathcal{P}') are reported with explicit reference to the global DH velocity calibration (NA, magnification, interferometer geometry). Median–level teacher losses are always defined on angle–invariant or calibration–light quantities to avoid propagating local angle errors from the LS+LM pipeline into the PINN.

9 AC Energetics (per Length)

$$\mathcal{P}'_{\text{diss},n} = \frac{1}{2} \Re\{G_n Q_n^*\} = \frac{1}{2} |Q_n|^2 \Re\{H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)\}, \quad \mathcal{P}'_{\text{store},n} = \frac{1}{2} \Im\{G_n Q_n^*\} = \frac{1}{2} |Q_n|^2 \Im\{H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)\}.$$

$$\text{Totals: } \mathcal{P}'_{\text{diss}} = \sum_{n \geq 1} \mathcal{P}'_{\text{diss},n}, \quad \mathcal{P}'_{\text{store}} = \sum_{n \geq 1} \mathcal{P}'_{\text{store},n}.$$

10 Estimation, QC, and Uncertainty (All Harmonics)

Inner regression (classical LS MW–W). Weighted complex LS on $(B_n \star h, \Psi_n \star h)$ to estimate C_n, D_n given (R_0, ν, h) , followed by a low-dimensional LM refinement of (R_0, ν, PSF) per subject/acquisition when needed. For each harmonic n , the design matrix

$$X_n(r) = [(B_n \star h)(r) \quad (\Psi_n \star h)(r)]$$

and the radial weights $W_n(r)$ (typically SNR-based with rim taper) define a weighted LS problem whose solution provides a baseline set of gains (C_n, D_n) , residual magnitude and phase RMS, and a condition number $\kappa(X_n)$ for identifiability checks.

PINN refinement and LS-guided distillation. The PINN is trained on the same DH profiles with physics-informed losses as described above. For segments and eyes that pass LS+LM QC, the LS+LM MW–W metrics are used to define the teacher losses $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,seg}}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,med}}$. In deployment, both LS+LM and PINN outputs can be reported side by side, with the PINN regarded as the preferred estimator in ill-conditioned regimes (low SNR, small α_n) and the LS+LM pipeline serving as a sanity check and a source of historical comparators.

Uncertainty. Cycle bootstrap, axial median aggregation, and parameter ensembles are used as described in [Section 4.3](#). We report median [IQR] and 95% CIs for $|R_n|/R_0$, $|Q_n|$, $|\tau_n|$, $\phi_{R|Q,n}$, $\phi_{\tau|Q,n}$, $H_{G|Q}(\omega_n)$, both at the segment level and as QC-filtered medians across segments.

Viscosity uncertainty propagation. At first order,

$$\text{Var}[Q_n] \approx \left(\frac{\partial Q_n}{\partial \nu} \right)^2 \text{Var}[\nu], \quad \frac{\partial Q_n}{\partial \nu} = \pi R_0^2 C_n K'(\alpha_n) \frac{\partial \alpha_n}{\partial \nu}, \quad \frac{\partial \alpha_n}{\partial \nu} = -\frac{1}{2} R_0 \sqrt{\omega_n} \nu^{-3/2}.$$

We report this contribution alongside bootstrap CIs when ν is treated as a random subject-level quantity in a prior band (e.g. $[2, 4] \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) even if the fit uses a fixed nominal value (e.g. $3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$).

QC gates (targets). $\text{SNR}_n \geq 6\text{--}10 \text{ dB}$; residual magnitude RMS ≤ 0.12 ; residual phase RMS ≤ 0.15 ; $\kappa(X_n) \leq 10^3$; PSF adequacy gain ≥ 0.2 and $\Delta\text{AICc} \geq 2$ versus a no-PSF model; and, after axial pooling, circular confidence intervals for key phases $\lesssim 20^\circ$. The LS+LM QC gates define the HQ set \mathcal{S}_{HQ} used in $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,seg}}$ and the per-eye medians used in $\mathcal{L}_{\text{teach,med}}$.

11 Common Failure Modes and Mitigations

12 Reporting Set (per Segment, per Harmonic)

$$R_0, \alpha_n, C_n, D_n, Q_n, \tau_n, G_n, H_{G|Q}(\omega_n), H_{R|Q}(\omega_n), H_{\tau|Q}(\omega_n), \phi_{R|Q,n}, \phi_{\tau|Q,n}, \phi_{G|Q,n},$$

with QC metrics and 95% CIs; mark artery/vein and axial span. Provide time-domain reconstructions for $v(r, t)$, $Q(t)$, $\tau(t)$ using retained harmonics. At the eye/cohort level, report QC-filtered medians and IQRs of Tier 1 metrics, and document whether they come from the classical LS+LM pipeline, the PINN, or their combination.

Units and Symbols

Symbol	Units	Meaning
R_0	m	Baseline radius
$A_0 = \pi R_0^2$	m ²	Baseline area
$V_n(r)$	m/s	Complex n -th harmonic velocity profile
C_n, D_n	m/s	Drive / moving-wall gains (harmonic n)
$\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0$	rad/s	Cardiac pulsation, f_0 in Hz
$\omega_n = n\omega_0$	rad/s	Harmonic angular frequency
$\nu, \mu = \rho\nu$	m ² /s, Pa s	Kinematic / dynamic viscosity
$\alpha_n = R_0\sqrt{\omega_n/\nu}$	–	Womersley number (harmonic n)
$\lambda_n = e^{i3\pi/4}\alpha_n$	–	Complex Womersley argument
B_n, Ψ_n	–	Rigid shape / log-radius sensitivity
$K(\alpha_n)$	–	Complex Womersley flow gain
h	–	Radial PSF (via \star)
$Q_n = \pi R_0^2 C_n K(\alpha_n)$	m ³ /s	Volumetric flow (harmonic n)
$G_n = i\omega_n \rho C_n$	Pa/m	Axial pressure-gradient harmonic
$\tau_n = \frac{\mu C_n \lambda_n J_1(\lambda_n)}{R_0 J_0(\lambda_n)}$	Pa	Wall shear stress (harmonic n)
$R_n/R_0 \simeq D_n/C_n$	–	Fractional wall kinematics (harmonic n)
$H_{G Q}(\omega_n) = G_n/Q_n$	Pa s/m ⁴	Per-length impedance-like transfer (pressure gradient / flow)
$ H_{G Q}(\omega_n) R_0^2$	Pa s/m ²	Geometry-normalized surface-impedance magnitude
$H_{R Q}(\omega_n) = (R_n/R_0)/Q_n$	s/m ³	Dilatation per unit pulsatile flow
$H_{\tau Q}(\omega_n) = \tau_n/Q_n$	Pa s/m ³	Shear per unit pulsatile flow
$\phi_{R Q,n}, \phi_{\tau Q,n}, \phi_{G Q,n}$	deg	Phases vs. flow
$\mathcal{P}'_{\text{diss},n} = \frac{1}{2}\Re\{G_n Q_n^*\}$	W/m	Dissipative AC power per length
$\mathcal{P}'_{\text{store},n} = \frac{1}{2}\Im\{G_n Q_n^*\}$	W/m	Reactive AC power per length

Open-Source Datasets and Pipelines

1. Dataset: [10.5281/zenodo.16761111](https://zenodo.org/record/16761111).
2. Hologram rendering: [HoloDoppler](#).
3. Velocity/flow estimation: [EyeFlow](#).

Table 1: Failure modes, likely causes, and mitigations.

Symptom	Likely cause	Mitigation
Unstable D_n estimate	Small α_n ; PSF blur $\Rightarrow B_n/\Psi_n$ collinearity	Increase rim weight; tighten PSF prior; mild Tikhonov on D_n ; drop $n = 2$ if failing QC; rely more on PINN physics terms and LS+LM median teacher loss rather than raw LS D_n values
High rim residuals	PSF mis-specification	Learn PSF meta; require adequacy gain ≥ 0.2 and $\Delta\text{AICc} \geq 2$; compare empirical LSF
Phase drift across z	Gating inconsistency or motion	Re-gate; enforce axial smoothness on R_0 ; reject segment; de-weight corresponding segments in the HQ teacher set